

Hubungan Antara Pembangunan Industri, Urbanisasi, dan Pertanian dengan Kualitas Air Sungai Citarum

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Abstract- This study aims to analyze the relationship between industrial development, urbanization, and agricultural activities on the water quality of the Citarum River. This river is an important source of water for more than 25 million people in West Java and DKI Jakarta, but it is now heavily polluted, especially in the upstream part. The study used a quantitative approach by distributing questionnaires through Google Form to 150 respondents in the area around the Citarum River flow. Data analysis was carried out using the SmartPLS statistical tool to test the causal relationship between variables. The three independent variables studied were industrial development (X1), urbanization (X2), and agriculture (X3), while the dependent variable was the water quality of the Citarum River (Y). The results showed that the three independent variables had a statistically significant effect on the decline in water quality. The t-statistical value for all three exceeded the threshold of 1.96 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating a high level of significance. An R² value of 0.587 indicates that 58.7% of water quality variations can be explained by these three factors. In terms of validity and reliability, industrial development constructs and water quality showed good results, while urbanization and agricultural constructs still had weaknesses in reliability even though they met discriminant validity. These findings confirm that the pollution of the Citarum River is a direct result of human activities, especially from the industrial sector, urban settlements, and practices

intensive farming. This research provides an empirical foundation for policy making

more sustainable water management in the Citarum watershed area.

Keywords: water quality, Citarum River, industrial development, urbanization, agriculture,

1. BACKGROUND

The Citarum River is the main source of water for 25 million people in West Java, including the DKI Jakarta and Bandung areas. [1] Water quality in the upper reaches of the Citarum River is in the category of "heavily polluted," especially during the rainy season due to surface runoff that carries pollutants from industries and settlements. [2] It was also found that the levels of heavy metals such as mercury (Hg), lead (Pb), and cadmium (Cd) in this river exceeded the WHO threshold. [3] Data from WEPA in 2017 noted that 60% of pollution comes from industrial waste, 30% from domestic waste, and 10% from agricultural practices that are not environmentally friendly. [1]

Water quality is the main indicator used to assess the physical, chemical, and biological conditions of a water body. Parameters such as Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), and pH reflect pollution levels and the health of aquatic ecosystems. The decrease in the value of these parameters is the main sign of degradation of the quality of the aquatic environment. [9] In the Citarum River, monitoring shows that many points do not meet water quality standards, especially in the upstream part of the river. [4] In addition, the index

Water quality experiences seasonal fluctuations that reflect the unstable ecological conditions of the river. [2]

Industrial development is a process of growth of the manufacturing sector that involves the use of chemicals and producing liquid waste on a large scale. Industrial waste discharged into water bodies generally contains ammonia, TDS, and heavy metals such as mercury and lead, which can harm aquatic life. [5] In the Citarum watershed, industrial estates have been shown to exert great pressure on water quality, especially downstream. [5] In fact, based on the analysis of the STORET method, the upstream part of the river shows a status of "heavily polluted" due to industrial activities without an adequate waste treatment system. [6]

Urbanization refers to the increase in population and the development of residential areas that lead to land conversion and an increase in the pollution burden from domestic waste. The growth of urban areas that is not balanced with good waste management infrastructure leads to an increase in COD and nutrient levels in the water. [7] In the context of the Citarum River, domestic waste from residential areas is one of the main contributors to water pollution, along with increased surface runoff due to reduced infiltration areas.

Agricultural activities are the dominant land use sector in the upstream part of the Citarum watershed. Uncontrolled use of fertilizers and pesticides can lead to the runoff of nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus into water bodies, especially during the rainy season. [8] This high nutrient content can trigger eutrophication, which is excessive algal growth, which ultimately lowers dissolved oxygen levels and disrupts the balance of aquatic ecosystems. [8]

This study aims to quantitatively analyze the relationship between industrial development (X1), urbanization (X2), and agriculture (X3) on the water quality of the Citarum River (Y). This study uses a statistical approach based on the SmartPLS model on the data obtained through surveys. Through this approach, it is hoped that an understanding of the contribution of each factor to water quality decline will be obtained as well as more targeted management recommendations.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Industrial development is the process of growth of the manufacturing sector and the economy through the construction of production facilities,

increasing operational capacity, and the use of chemicals in industrial processes. [5] This activity produces liquid waste that generally contains heavy metals, ammonia, and other organic matter that can contaminate water bodies. [5] If this waste does not go through an adequate treatment process, it will lead to an increase in the value of Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), and Total Suspended Solids (TSS), which are the main indicators of water quality degradation. [9] Thus, the more intensive the development of industries that are not environmentally friendly, the greater the impact on water quality degradation. [6]

Urbanization is the process of transforming the area from rural to urban which is characterized by an increase in population, infrastructure development, and land conversion. [11] The growth of residential areas and the reduction of green open space lead to increased surface runoff that carries nutrients, organic matter, and heavy metals to water bodies. [12] In addition, the lack of domestic waste management systems in urban areas has exacerbated water pollution. This has an impact on increased COD and TSS levels and decreased pH, which reflects a significant decline in water quality. [10]

Agriculture is a land use activity for the production of food crops and horticulture, which usually uses chemical fertilizers and pesticides to increase crop yields. [13] If not managed sustainably, these activities have the potential to result in runoff containing nitrogen, phosphorus, and harmful chemicals into water bodies. [13] The high nutrient content in water due to agricultural runoff can trigger overgrowth of algae (eutrophication), which ultimately lowers dissolved oxygen levels and disrupts the life of aquatic organisms. [8] Therefore, intensive agricultural practices that are not environmentally friendly are one of the significant causes of the decline in water quality. [8]

1. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative approach, which is a method that emphasizes objective measurement and statistical analysis of numerical data to test the relationship between variables. [13] Data collection was carried out through a Google Form questionnaire distributed to 150 respondents in the Bekasi area. The analysis tool used is SmartPLS to measure the causal relationship between variables.

Gambar 1. Model Penelitian

The hypotheses proposed in this study are: H1: Industrial Development (X1) has a negative effect on the Water Quality of the Citarum River (Y); H2: Urbanization (X2) has a negative effect on the Water Quality of the Citarum River (Y); and H3: Agriculture (X3) has a negative effect on the Water Quality of the Citarum River (Y).

Tabel 1: VARIABEL OPERASIONAL

Indicators	Code	Authors
Kualitas Air		
What are the pollution load management strategies implemented to improve the water quality of the Citarum River?	KA1	[1]
To evaluate the benefits and costs of wastewater and solid waste management to improve the living environment in the Citarum River.	KA2	[8]
Can economic policy tools improve community and industrial participation in Citarum River water quality improvement?	KA3	[7]
Pembangunan Industri		
What is the impact of development activities, including industrial waste, on the pollution level of the Citarum River?	PI1	[3]
To evaluate the effectiveness and cost-efficiency of wastewater treatment systems in industrial areas near the Citarum River.	PI2	[8]

Can economic incentives increase industry compliance with environmental regulations to reduce pollution in the Citarum River?	PI3	[7]
Urbanisasi		
How does urban population growth contribute to water pollution in the Citarum River basin?	UB1	[7]
What is the environmental impact of land use change due to rapid urbanization in the Citarum River area?	UB2	[7]
Pertanian		
To what extent does agricultural chemical usage contribute to nutrient pollution in the Citarum River?	PT1	[7]
What are the pathways and effects of agricultural runoff entering the Citarum River during rainy seasons?	PT2	[7]

1. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. RESPONDENT CHARACTERISTICS

In the process of collecting data through a questionnaire, a total of 150 respondents were obtained. As many as 60% are women and 40% are men. The majority of respondents were in the age range of 17-25 years at 84.7%, followed by the age group of 26-35 years old at 7.3%, the age group of 36-45 years at 4%, and the age over 45 years old at 4%. In terms of the last education, most of the respondents were Bachelor 1 graduates as much as 78.7%, then high school/vocational/equivalent graduates by 13.3%, and the rest graduated by Diploma (Diploma 1-3) by 8%. These findings show that respondents are dominated by the highly educated young generation, which is relevant in understanding the dynamics of digital marketing and customer engagement on social media platforms.

B. VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

Tabel 2: CONSTRUCT RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Composite reliability (rho_A)	Average variance extracted...
Kualitas Air (Y)	0.758	0.787	0.861	0.674
Pembangunan Industri(X1)	0.778	0.809	0.870	0.691
Pertanian(X3)	0.622	0.641	0.839	0.723
Urbanisasi(X2)	0.542	0.576	0.810	0.682

Based on the results of the reliability and validity tests displayed, it can be concluded that the Water Quality (Y) and Industrial Development (X1) constructs have good reliability because Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values both exceed 0.7. In addition, this construct also shows good convergent validity because the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value is greater than 0.5. On the other hand, the Agriculture construct (X3) has Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (rho_A) values below 0.7, which indicates its reliability is poor, although the rho_C and AVE values still qualify for convergent validity. Meanwhile, the Urbanization construct (X2) shows low reliability because all Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values are below 0.7, although the AVE still meets the convergent validity threshold (> 0.5).

Tabel 3: *DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY*

	Kualitas Air (Y)	Pembangunan Industri(X1)	Pertanian(X3)	Urbanisasi(X2)
Kualitas Air (Y)	0.821			
Pembangunan Industri(X1)	0.747	0.831		
Pertanian(X3)	0.561	0.502	0.851	
Urbanisasi(X2)	0.595	0.654	0.647	0.826

Based on the results of the discriminant validity test using the Fornell-Larcker criteria, it can be concluded that all constructs in the model have met the requirements of discriminant validity. This is indicated by the square root value of AVE (shown on the diagonal of the table) for each larger construct compared to the correlation between other constructs in the same column/row. For example, the diagonal value for Water Quality (Y) of 0.821 is higher than its correlation with Industrial Development (X1) of 0.747, Agriculture (X3) of 0.561, and Urbanization (X2) of 0.595. A similar pattern is also seen in other constructs, such as Industrial Development (X1) with a diagonal value of 0.831 which is greater than the correlation with other constructs. Thus, the model has demonstrated good discriminant validity, which means that each construct in the model is able to distinguish itself clearly from the others.

C. UJI HIPOTESIS

Gambar 2. Model *Bootstrapping*

Based on the results of the visualization of the structural model (inner model) in the diagram above, it can be seen that the three independent variables, namely Industrial Development (X1), Urbanization (X2), and Agriculture (X3), all have t-statistical values above 1.96 against the dependent variable Water Quality (Y). This is indicated by the p-value displayed as 0.000, which means it is much smaller than the general significance limit ($\alpha = 0.05$). Therefore, it can be concluded that these three variables have a significant effect on Water Quality (Y). In addition, the R² value of 0.587 in Water Quality shows that the three independent variables are able to explain 58.7% of the variation that occurs in Water Quality.

1. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis from Chapter 1 to Chapter 4, this study concludes that the three independent variables, namely industrial development, urbanization, and agriculture, have a significant influence on the water quality of the Citarum River. This is proven through structural model testing using SmartPLS, where the three influence pathways show a t-statistic value above 1.96 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant. In terms of reliability and validity, the Industrial Development and Water Quality construct shows Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values above 0.7, as well as AVE above 0.5, which means it has good internal consistency and convergent validity. Although the Urbanization and Agriculture constructs show some weaknesses in reliability, they still meet discriminant validity based on the Fornell-Larcker criteria. An R² value of 0.587 indicates that the variation in water quality can be explained by 58.7% by these three factors, so it can be said that the model used is strong enough to menggambarkan fenomena pencemaran air di Sungai Citarum akibat aktivitas manusia.

This study draws on the conceptual framework and previous findings, especially from Yokosawa & Mizunoya (2022) who emphasize the importance of economic policy approaches in controlling industrial pollution, as well as from Kerstens et al. (2016) who highlight the cumulative impact of domestic and agricultural waste on the Citarum River ecosystem. By combining an empirical approach and the support of the scientific literature, this research contributes to scientific understanding and policy in managing water resources in river areas that are crucial for the lives of millions of people.

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